

Carrot & Stick
by Brian Paul Kaess

In September 2003 or so, I spent about two weeks in Madden Mental Health facility in Maywood, Illinois, being evaluated by their staff. At some point, a female medical student chatted with me and said my wife had accused me of choking her even though my version of the story was that I only pushed her (which was the truth- there was no attempt to choke). The medical student said, however, that if I went along with the wife's version of the story, they would eventually release me, and let me return home to my family. So she was using a bit of a carrot-and-stick approach and didn't care about my version of the story. So I agreed to what she proposed in order just to go home to my family. I did note however that she used this carrot-and-stick approach instead of just going with my story.

Also, during the same two week stay at Madden, I was interviewed by a black social worker on some of my habits. I told him at one point that I had only one drink in the last two years, and he wrote something down on his report that was different than what I said. That's the bottom line. He wrote that I drank two or more times during a certain time period or something similar. This was a false statement and I noticed that right away. He was overstating my drinking behavior which was extremely minimal by my early 30's. So that one looked like a false report and I can confirm that if I saw the report again.

Well that's enough about that,
Brian